
I found model testing (e.g., with pytest) useful to ensure the correctness of model behavior in key usage scenarios.

I found data testing (e.g., with Great Expectations) useful to assure the quality of data used for model training.

I found implementing an API for ML (e.g., using FastAPI) useful to foster the interoperability of our ML components.

I found containerization (e.g., with Docker and Docker Compose) useful to foster the portability and ease of deployment of our ML components.

I found the adoption of CI/CD practices (e.g., using GitHub Actions) useful to streamline the end-to-end development and ML processes.

I found resource monitoring (e.g., with Better Uptime, Prometheus, and Grafana) useful to ensure the correct functioning of our ML components in production.

I found model performance monitoring (e.g., drift detection with Alibi Detect) useful to ensure correct and consistent behavior of our production models over time.

2. Do you want to leave some comments about the usefulness of applying software engineering good practices to build an ML-based component? Would you use them in future data science projects? *

**The amount of work was
equally distributed across
the milestones.**

6. Do you want to leave some comments regarding the above project activities?

7. How easy was it for your team in the laboratory to build and deploy an ML component? *
Which are the main problems that you overcame?

8. Overall, would you recommend this course to your colleagues for next year? *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

- Definitely not!
 Not likely
 Likely
 Definitely!

9. Do you want to leave any other comment before submitting your answers?
